

HYDROTHERMAL AGING OF JUTE FIBER REINFORCED POLYPROPYLENE INJECTION MOLDINGS

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1 Introduction

Environmental issue has been important rapidly because of the global warming and oil resource saving. In composite materials inorganic fibers such as glass fibers and carbon fibers are common fibers as reinforcement, however, it brings some difficulty for recycling these composite materials. Instead of these inorganic fibers natural fibers can be used as reinforcement of the composite materials [1-5]. The natural fibers possess low density and sometimes equivalent stiffness to glass fibers. The most important thing is non-usage of oil resources during fabrication of the fibers. However, there are several points which we have to overcome in natural fiber composites. One of these key issues is the influence of water environment on the physical properties of natural fiber composites. Usually natural fibers have reactive function, so that it is easy to absorb the water. Even in glass fiber reinforced composites the reduction of mechanical properties occurs after exposing them to water environment. From this fact, therefore, it is easily supposed that the high amount of water absorption brings significant reduction of mechanical properties in natural fiber composites.

From this background, this paper discussed the influence of water on jute fiber reinforced polypropylene injection molded composites by exposing hydrothermal environment. The aging behaviors were discussed by weight changes and tensile properties. In addition, the influence of fiber content on hydrothermal properties was also discussed.

2 Experimental Procedure

Materials used were jute fiber filled polypropylene (jute/PP) pellet and neat polypropylene (PP) pellet. The jute/PP pellet was

the long fiber type (LFT) pellet produced by pultrusion process, and the weight fraction of jute fiber in jute/PP pellet was 50wt%. By dry-blending of jute/PP and neat PP pellet 5 kinds of jute/PP dumbbell-shaped specimens with different fiber content (10wt%, 20wt%, 30wt%, 40wt% and 50wt%) were prepared as listed in Table 1.

In order to discuss the influence of water absorption on weight changes and tensile properties all the specimens were aged under hydrothermal environment. Before the water immersion all the specimens were dried at 100°C under the vacuum condition. After drying the specimens were immersed in distilled water at 80°C for 3, 10, 30, 100, 300, 1000 and 3000 hours. After the fixed periods of immersion the weight changes and the mechanical properties were evaluated.

Weight changes by hydrothermal aging were evaluated as follows. Before the water immersion the weight of dried specimen before immersion, W_o , was weighed and the specimens were immersed. After the fixed periods of immersion the specimens were taken away from the water bath, and the weight of wet specimen, W_w , was weighed. After weighing W_w the specimens were dried again and the weight of dried specimen after immersion, W_d , was weighed.

Table 1 Composition of materials used.

Specimen ID	Blend ratio (wt%)		Jute fiber content (wt%)
	Jute/PP pellet	Neat PP pellet	
PP	0	100	0
Jute10	20	80	10
Jute20	40	60	20
Jute30	60	40	30
Jute40	80	20	40
Jute50	100	0	50

From W_o , W_w and W_d the weight change parameters, M_g , and M_l , were evaluated by

$$M_g = \frac{W_w - W_d}{W_o} \quad (1)$$

$$M_l = \frac{W_o - W_d}{W_o} \quad (2)$$

Here, M_g corresponded to the weight gain due to water absorption and M_l corresponded to the weight reduction by material loss.

The influence of water on the mechanical properties was evaluated by the static tensile test. Tensile test was performed for the specimens soon after the hydrothermal aging (containing environmental water) and the dried specimens after aging. The tensile tests were performed at a constant cross-head speed of 2mm/min under room temperature, and the tensile moduli and strengths were evaluated.

3 Experimental Results and Discussion

Fig.1 shows the changes of the weight gain, M_g , against the square root of aging time. In neat PP specimen the increase of M_g was a little. On the other hand, M_g of jute/PP specimens showed significant increase with increasing the aging time. In the specimens with the fiber content below 20wt% M_g increased gradually, while the specimens with the fiber content above 30wt% showed rapid increase of M_g . Eventually M_g at 300 hours reached more than 10%. In case of the glass fiber/PP composite M_g reached less than 1%, and it reached saturation. Soon after the immersion the specimen swelled and the thickness expanded in the specimens with high fiber content. However, the thickness

Fig.1 Changes of the weight gain, M_g .

recovered by leaving it in air. From these results it is easily concluded that high M_g was brought by the water absorption of jute fiber itself.

Fig.2 shows the changes of the weight loss, M_l , against the square root of immersion time. In neat PP and jute10 M_l was almost zero. However, M_l increased markedly in the specimens with 20wt% and more of jute fiber. Neat PP did not show any material loss, and therefore the material loss of jute/PP composites was derived by the loss of jute fiber. This was supposed by the color change of environmental water to dark brown after long-term immersion.

Fig.3 shows the tensile stress-strain curves for the virgin specimens. The stress-strain curves drastically changed with increasing the jute fiber content below 20wt%. However, the tendency of the stress-strain curves for the specimens with 30wt% and more fiber content, and only the failure stress changed depending on the fiber content. Fig.4

Fig.2 Changes of the weight loss, M_l .

Fig.3 Tensile stress-strain curves for the virgin specimens.

Fig.4 Comparisons of tensile moduli and strengths of the virgin specimens.

Fig.5 Changes of the tensile moduli after immersion for wet specimens.

Fig.6 Changes of the tensile moduli after immersion for dried specimens.

summarizes the tensile moduli and strengths of the virgin specimens. The tensile moduli increased with increasing the jute fiber content, and it showed almost the linear correlation. The tensile strengths also increased with increasing the fiber content,

Fig.7 Changes of the tensile strengths after immersion for wet specimens.

Fig.8 Changes of the tensile strengths after immersion for dried specimens.

however, they decreased in the specimens with the fiber content of 40 and 50wt%. Too much fiber brought the undesirable effect on the tensile strength.

Fig.5 shows the changes of the tensile modulus by aging for the wet specimens. In neat PP specimen the moduli were almost constant even after aging. On the contrary, the moduli of the jute/PP composites showed significant reduction by aging, and the drastic drop was observed in the specimen with higher fiber content. Fig.6 shows the changes of the tensile modulus by aging for the dried specimens. The modulus slightly recovered by drying, however, the tendency was almost the same. Therefore it is considered that the modulus reduction was caused by the degradation of jute fiber and jute fiber/PP interface.

Fig.7 shows the changes of the tensile strength by aging for the wet specimens. In neat PP the strength did not change even after immersion. On

Fig.4 Comparisons of tensile moduli and strengths of the virgin specimens.

the other hand, the significant strength reduction occurred in jute/PP specimens. The aging time when the strength of jute/PP reached lower than neat PP became shorter with increasing jute fiber content. After 3000 hours immersion, the strength became lower with increasing jute fiber content. Fig.8 shows the changes of the tensile strength by aging for the dried specimens. The strength reduction of these dried specimens was the same tendency with Fig.7. From these results the remained water in the specimen did not affect the strength reduction. Thus, the water absorption of jute fiber did not affect the strength reduction. The strength of jute/PP after long aging reached much lower than the neat PP, and this result suggested that jute fiber did not play as reinforcement of PP. Jute fiber did not carry the applied load, and it might exist as making defect in PP matrix. It is considered that the adhesion between jute fiber and PP after aging disappeared and that the fracture initiated from the debonded interface between jute fiber and PP. This brought quite lower strength after immersion of jute/PP specimens.

From these results, the degradation mechanism of the jute/PP composites was discussed. Fig.9 summarizes the degradation mechanism. By water immersion the jute fiber absorbed the water, and it swelled and expanded. By swelling the adhesion between jute fiber and PP matrix was weakened. In addition, the swelled jute fiber shrank by drying, and it brought the gap between jute fiber and PP. As a result, the reinforcing effect of jute fiber disappeared, and the significant reduction of mechanical properties was induced.

4 Conclusion

This study discussed the influence of water on jute fiber reinforced polypropylene injection molded composites. The jute fiber easily absorbed the water and it brings the degradation of the jute fiber and fiber/PP interface. Such degradation brought the significant reduction of the mechanical properties.

References

- [1] T. T. L. Doan, S. L. Gao and E. Mäder, "Jute/polypropylene composites I. Effect of matrix modification", *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, Vol.66, pp.952-963, 2006.
- [2] J. M. Park, S. T. Quang, B. S. Hwang and K. L. DeVries, "Interfacial evaluation of modified jute and hemp fibers/polypropylene (PP)-maleic anhydride polypropylene copolymers (PP-MAPP) composites using micromechanical technique and nondestructive acoustic emission", *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, Vol.66, pp.2686-2699, 2006.
- [3] T. T. L. Doan, H. Brodowsky and E. Mäder, "Jute fibre/polypropylene composites II. thermal, hydrothermal and dynamic mechanical behaviour", *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, Vol.67, pp.2707-2714, 2007.
- [4] J. M. Park, P. G. Kim, J. H. Jang, Z. Wang, B. S. Hwang and K. L. DeVries, "Interfacial evaluation and durability of modified jute fibers/polypropylene (PP) composites using micromechanical test and acoustic emission", *Composites Part B*, Vol.39, pp.1042-1061, 2008.
- [5] N. Sgriccia, M. C. Hawley and M. Misra, "Characterization of natural fiber surfaces and natural fiber composites", *Composites Part A*, Vol.39, pp.1632-1637, 2008.